

Epidemiological Situation of Leprosy in the Littoral Region of Cameroon

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aimed at determining the epidemiological situation of leprosy in the Littoral region of Cameroon.

Problem: 20 years after the elimination of leprosy as a public health problem in Cameroon, we wondered about its epidemiological situation across the country and in particular in the Littoral region.

Methods: We conducted a quantitative retrospective, descriptive cross-sectional study. The data were collected from the patients' registers at the Dibamba leprosarium from 2011 to 2021. Using data from the Dibamba leprosarium, which appeared to be the only reference health facility still well engaged in the fight against leprosy in the Littoral region, we were able to create a clear leprosy situational report.

Results: 281 cases of leprosy were treated at the Dibamba leprosarium, representing an incidence of 28 cases per year. They came from several regions of the country and even from a neighboring country (Central African Republic). 257 (91.50%) cases came from 20 health districts out of 24 in the Littoral region. Men were more represented with 156 (55.5%) cases. 14 (5%) cases were children under 15 years old, an average of 1 case per year. 22.9% (n= 44) of people affected by leprosy had second degree disabilities. 90.75% (n=255) of cases received were of the multibacillary form (MB). 44.4% (n=125) of female patients had a clinical form of MB.

Conclusion: This situational report has shown that the Littoral region is still very endemic for Leprosy. Rapid actions should be taken to definitively stop the transmission of this disease.

Introduction

Leprosy is a neglected tropical disease (NTD) still present in more than 120 countries, with more than 200,000 new cases reported each year, it is often linked to poor socioeconomic conditions. This infectious disease causes the greatest number of physical difficulties [1]. In Africa, 38 countries reported more than one case in 2019. Also, 20,209 (18 per million population) new cases were reported in Africa, with 2,150 (5.2 per million children) new pediatric cases and

2,933 (2.6 per million inhabitants) new cases with degree 2 disability [2]. Leprosy still remains present in several African countries such as: the Central African Republic, Burkina Faso, Togo [3,4,5].

In Cameroon, the leprosy elimination threshold (prevalence less than 1/10,000) was reached in 2000. In 2015, 361 new cases of leprosy were detected in Cameroon with a national prevalence of 0.23 cases per 10 000 inhabitants. It has remained below 1/10,000 inhabitants since the elimination threshold was

More Information

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reached. The leprosy elimination threshold was reached by all 10 regions of Cameroon in 2014, but 12 health districts have not yet reached this threshold. It is noted that between 2000 and 2014 the overall burden of leprosy decreased considerably [6]. However, in 2015, leprosy was still actively transmitted in the community with high contagiousness and diagnosis was lately made [7].

20 years after the elimination of leprosy in Cameroon, all structures of the national leprosy control program have been dismantled. Health personnel are no more trained for leprosy control and the rarity of cases has caused the loss of Leprosy epidemiological situation. Only the leprosariums considered as places of isolation and care for leprosy patients continued to provide the minimum service. The reduction in the overall burden of leprosy has led to a sharp decline in the resources of these leprosariums. The number of leprosariums has fallen from 46 to only 5 to date and 3 to 1 in the Littoral region. The Dibamba leprosarium as the only leprosy care center in the Littoral region receives patients from all surrounding regions. All this leads us to think that the leprosy situation in Cameroon in general and in the Littoral region in particular could undoubtedly be more alarming than we imagine.

This study aimed at determining the epidemiological situation of leprosy 10 years after its elimination as a public health problem in the Littoral region of Cameroon. More specifically, we highlight the socio-demographic characteristics and describe the clinical profile of people affected by leprosy in the Littoral region from 2011 to 2021.

Materials and Methods

This was a retrospective and cross-sectional quantitative descriptive study carried out in the Littoral region of Cameroon. This region was chosen because it has one of the few leprosy care centers still operational in the region. This study was carried out on all patients treated for leprosy from 2011 to 2021 at the Dibamba leprosarium and patients' health districts of origin. Information on patients treated for leprosy from 2011 to 2021 was obtained from registers available at the Dibamba leprosarium. These were obtained using an individual data collection questionnaire. The data obtained were processed and analyzed using Excel 2016 and SPSS 25.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of people affected by leprosy

Between 2011 and 2021, 281 cases of leprosy were treated at the Dibamba leprosarium, representing an incidence of **28 cases per year**. Male individuals were more represented with 156 (55.5%) cases. 91.50% (n=257) came from the Littoral region and 0.40% (n=1) from the Central African Republic.

Table 1: Region of origin of patients treated at the Dibamba leprosarium between 2011 and 2021

Region of origin of patients	Number	Proportion
Centre	6	2.10%
Littoral	257	91.50%
Nord-Ouest	1	0.40%
Ouest	3	1.10%
République centrafricaine (RCA)	1	0.40%
Sud	5	1.80%
Sud-Ouest	4	1.40%
Données manquantes	4	1.40%
Total	281	100

Table 2 shows that people affected by leprosy came from almost all the districts of the Littoral region, i.e. 20 out of 24 districts. Nevertheless, No cases of leprosy come from the districts of Melong, Nkondjock, Njoumbe Penja and Ndom. The districts with the lowest number of cases were Manoka : 1 case (0.4%) and Mbanga : 1 case (0.4%). The district with the highest number of cases was Déido, with 46 cases (17.9%).

Table 2: Breakdown of patients received in the Littoral region according to their area of origin

Area of origin	Number	Proportion
Manoka	1	0,40%
Mbanga	1	0,40%
Dibombari	2	0,80%
Loum	2	0,80%
Abo	4	1,60%
Boko	4	1,60%
Manjo	4	1,60%
Nylon	5	1,90%
Yabassi	6	2,30%
Nkongsamba	8	3,10%
Pouma	10	3,90%
Ngambe	11	4,30%
Bonassama	15	5,80%
Cité des palmiers	17	6,60%
Japoma	19	7,40%
Bangue	24	9,30%
New bell	25	9,70%
Logbaba	26	10,10%
Edea	27	10,50%
Deido	46	17,90%
Total	257	100%

According to table 3, between 2011 and 2021, 257 cases from the Littoral region were received at the Dibamba leprosarium. Overall, there is a fluctuation in leprosy patient number from 2011 to 2021 with a high

pick of 37 patients received in 2017 representing 14.40% of all patients follow at the leprosarium of Dibamba within that given timeframe.

Table 3: Distribution of leprosy cases in the Littoral region per year

Year	Number	Proportion
2011	28	10.90%
2012	18	7%
2013	21	8.20%
2014	18	7%
2015	28	10.90%
2016	24	9.30%
2017	37	14.40%
2018	30	11.70%
2019	31	12.10%
2020	14	5.40%
2021	8	3.10%
Total	257	100%

Clinical profile of people affected by leprosy

Among lepers in the Littoral region of Cameroon from 2011 to 2021, 5% (n=14) of the leprosy cases received were under 15 years old children, making an average of 1 case per year. 22.9% (n= 44) of people affected by leprosy had second-degree disabilities. It is important to note that data on disability due to leprosy are only available from 2014. 90.75% (n=255) of cases received were multibacillary (MB) lepers. 44.4% (n=125) of female patients have an MB clinical form.

Table 4 shows that leprosy cases for under 15 years old children were reported in nine health districts of the Littoral region. The Logbaba health district reported the highest number of cases with 23% (n=3) of all cases.

Table 4: Distribution of under 15 years old children leprosy cases according to their area of origin

District of origin	Leprosy cases for under 15 years old children	
	Number	Proportion
Bangue	1	8%
Boko	1	8%
Bonassama	1	8%
Edea	1	8%
New bell	1	8%
Nkongsamba	1	8%
Deido	2	15%
Nylon	2	15%
Logbaba	3	23%
Total	13	100%

Discussion

Incidence rate of leprosy in the Littoral region

Our study focused on describing the epidemiological situation of leprosy over the last 10 years after its

elimination as a public health problem in the Littoral region. Overall, 281 cases of leprosy were treated at the Dibamba leprosarium, representing an incidence of 28 cases per year. 91.50% (n=257) of cases came from the Littoral region. The other 8.5% (24) of cases came from other districts of Cameroon and one case from the neighboring of Central African Republic. As we can see, the Dibamba leprosarium plays a major role in the care of leprosy, not only in Cameroon, but also in the Central African sub-region. It should be remembered that the Dibamba leprosarium is a faith-based health facility created in 1954. It is managed by a Catholic religious congregation and benefits from funding from various partners in Spain. The latter has long worked to achieve the objectives of eliminating leprosy in Cameroon. It has always positioned itself as a health facility of excellence for the treatment of leprosy.

Among the 281 patients received during the study period, we observed a predominance of males. In fact, our sample had 55.5% (n=156) male patients. Our results are identical to those found by Ruhanga [8] in the Democratic Republic of Congo and Dioussé et al. [9] in Senegal with 55.3% and 59% respectively. Therefore, any program designs for leprosy elimination should target **elderly men in priority**.

Leprosy cases with degree 2 disability

Table 5: Distribution of leprosy cases with degree 2 disability per patient's areas of origin

Leprosy cases with degree 2 disability		
District of origin	Number	Proportion
Bangue	5	11,4%
Boko	1	2,3%
Bonassama	3	6,8%
Cité des palmiers	1	2,3%
Deido	4	9,1%
Edea	6	13,6%
Japoma	3	6,8%
Logbaba	2	4,5%
Loum	2	4,5%
Manjo	2	4,5%
Mbanga	1	2,3%
New bell	3	6,8%
Ngambe	2	4,5%
Nkongsamba	2	4,5%
Nylon	1	2,3%
Pouma	1	2,3%
Yabassi	3	6,8%
Autres régions	2	4,5%
Total	42	100,00%

Table 5 shows that all districts reported category 2 disabilities associated with leprosy in the Littoral region. These are lesions observed in patients with active leprosy. The presence of cases with these

disabilities indicates that leprosy detection is being done late in all districts. This argument allows us to confirm that the impression of cessation in leprosy transmission in the littoral region would have been caused by a lack of activity in health services concerning leprosy management.

Multibacillary (MB) lepers in the Littoral region

Our results showed that 90.75% (n=255) of patients have the MB form of leprosy and among these cases, 44.4% (n=125) were found in women. This proportion was higher than that found in Chad from 2015 to 2019 (83.10%) [10]. This high proportion of MB lepers in the Littoral region of Cameroon reflects a high contagiousness of the disease. In fact, People with MB leprosy are more contagious and therefore more involved in the transmission of this disease. This proportion involves a shift from active case detection to passive detection and signals the need to implement interventions aimed at detection. The proportion of MB forms is also used to calculate drug requirements. Once again this indicator reflects the level of exposure of the general population, as we know that women find themselves at the center of life in the society.

Pediatric cases of leprosy in the Littoral region

In our sample, we found 5% (n=14) cases of leprosy in children under 15 years old. This proportion is well above that recommended by the current WHO leprosy elimination strategy, which is zero cases of leprosy in children [1]. However, it is lower than that in Chad from 2015 to 2019 (7.92%) [10] and in Togo from 2000 to 2014 (5.5%) [11]. Such a proportion of leprosy cases among children of under 15 years old indicates that leprosy continues to be transmitted very actively within the community. However, cases of leprosy in children of under 15 years of old have been reported in nine health districts, among which Logbaba is in the lead with 21.4% (n=3) of all cases. These are the districts where the transmission of leprosy remains very active. The analysis of table 6 shows that since 2019, no cases of leprosy have been reported in children of under 15 years old. However, we still wonder if this is an under-reporting or the cessation of leprosy transmission for under 15 years old children in the region.

Table 6: Distribution of under 15 years old children leprosy cases per year

under 15 years old children leprosy		
Year	Number	Proportion
2011	1	7.1%
2012	3	21.4%
2013	2	14.3%
2014	1	7.1%
2015	2	14.3%
2016	0	0.0%
2017	2	14.3%
2018	2	14.3%

2019	0	0.0%
2020	1	7.1%
2021	0	0.0%
Total	14	100.00%

Conclusion

At the end of our study which aimed at determining the epidemiological situation of leprosy 10 years after its elimination as a public health problem in the Littoral region of Cameroon, the analysis of the leprosy indicators showed that the Littoral region was still very endemic for leprosy. Also, disease transmission remained very active. In fact, all health districts were endemic for this disease.

Concerning socio-demographic characteristics leprosy patients in the littoral region of Cameroon, we found that from 2011 to 2021, 281 cases of leprosy were treated at the Dibamba leprosarium representing an incidence of 28 cases per year. These patients came from several regions of the country and even from a neighboring country (Central African Republic). 257 or 91.50% of cases came from 20 health districts out of the 24 health districts of the Littoral region. Male individuals were more represented with 156 (55.5%) cases.

For the clinical profile of people affected by leprosy in the Littoral region from 2011 to 2021, 14 cases or 5% were children of under 15 years old which represented an average of 1 case per year. 22.9% (n= 44) of people affected by leprosy had second degree disabilities. 90.75% (n=255) of the cases received were of the multibacillary form (MB) and 44.4% (n=125) of female patients had a clinical form of MB.

While on the ground, we learned that the fight against leprosy had been integrated into the minimum package of activities. But a more in-depth analysis revealed: a decline in leprosy elimination activities, multidrug therapy (MDT) is not available in health facilities and health personnel are no longer trained in the management of leprosy since a long moment. The Dibamba leprosarium, already transformed into a reference center, remains the most active health facility in the fight against leprosy. Its attractiveness goes beyond the Littoral region, or even the entire country, and even extends to neighboring countries.

At the end of this study, it appears urgent to actively relaunch activities to fight leprosy in order to prevent the situation from worsening towards urban leprosy which is very difficult to manage. Furthermore, similar studies must be carried out in all other regions of the country to have a precise idea of endemic leprosy in Cameroon.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] OMS. Vers zéro lèpre. Stratégie mondiale de Lutte contre la lèpre (Maladie de Hansen) 2021–2030 . [2021]cité 1juill 2021]. Available at: http://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/341762?search-result=true&query=STRATEGIE+LEPRE&scope=&rpp=10&sort_by=score&order=desc
- [2] OMS. Weekly Epidemiological Record, 2020, vol. 95, 36 [full issue]. Wkly Epidemiol Rec Relevé Épidémiologique Hebd Sept2020;95(36):417-40.
- [3] Um Boock A, Ntozo'o JP, Boua B, Vander Plaetse B. Evidence of high endemicity of leprosy and yaws in the municipality of Balé-Loko in the Central African Republic. *Med Sante Trop.* May 2019;29(2):155-8.
- [4] Ouédraogo A, Ilboudo LW, Sermé M, Sanou LM, Marcellin B, Yacouba N, et al. dépistage de La Lèpre en stratégie avancée dans Les régions du Centre ouest et du Centre nord du BurKina Faso. ALLF. 2019;
- [5] Kombaté K, Teclessou J, Saka B, Tabe-Djato G, Akakpo S, Mouhari-Toure A, et al. Leprosy in Togo: retrospective study of 2630 cases over 15 years. *Our Dermatol Online.* 23 Nov 2017;8:10-4.
- [6] Tabah EN, Nsagha DS, Bissek ACZK, Bratschi MW, Njamnshi TN, Pluschke G, et al. Correction: The Burden of Leprosy in Cameroon: Fifteen Years into the Post-elimination Era. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* Jan 2016;11(1):e0005305.
- [7] Tabah EN. le rapport du comité national de lutte contre le pian, la leishmaniose, la lèpre et l'ulcère de buruli 2015. 2016.
- [8] Ruhanga M. Le Profil épidémiologique, clinique et thérapeutique de la Lèpre à l'est de la République Démocratique du Congo. 1 Jun 2019;Original research.
- [9] Dioussé P, Dione H, Bammo M, Gueye N, Diallo TAA, Seck F, et al. [Leprosy in children in the region of Thiès, Senegal: study determining whether or not it is a signal of recrudescence]. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2017;27:174.
- [10] Kabo AK, Kaman K, Doungous DM, Ouedraogo L, Abakar M, Godreuil S, et al. [Epidemiology of leprosy in Chad from 2015 to 2019]. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2022;41:120.
- [11] Teclessou JN, Saka B, Akakpo AS, Tabe-Djato GL, Amedifou YDC, Mouhari-Toure A, et al. [Retrospective Study of Leprosy in Togo (2000-2014): about 2,630 cases]. *Bull Soc Pathol Exot* 1990. 2018;111(2):99-103.

